

Breaking the Barriers: The Experiences of Women Principal in School: An Auto-Ethnography

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Abstract: In this paper I have tried to examine the experience of women principals in government school's in Nepal. Getting birth in a mixed ethnic family, spent a lot of time working in private institution since 2061-2066. And then with perseverance and fortitude made the move to government service. Using introspection and critical reading of pertinent academic literature I have tried to explore the intersection of gender, caste, p ethnicity and regional identity. Through the use of auto ethnography as a method and genre I have tried to draw the attention to the institutional support gaps systematic impediments and revolutionary leadership practices that arose in spite of this limitations. The study adds to discussions about intersectionality feminist leadership and restructuring Nepal educational system.

Keywords: *Nepal government school's Intersectional, Auto ethnography women Principals and hurdles.*

Introduction

In this article I have tried to look into my personal journey from teaching in a private school to being the principal of government school in Nepal. The Intersection of several identities being married into a Malayali household and having a Father from the Yadav community and mother from the Chhetri communities has influenced my Story. My experience are both enhanced and complicated by these hybrid identity created by these overlapping social cultural and regional ties. When navigating these many social settings I came across profoundly ingrained gender stereotypes, caste based prejudices and structural injustice. Despite my commitment and credentials the early years of my teaching career in a private school where characterized by a lack of recognition and little opportunity for professional development. In the year 2066 I entered into government school as a PC a teacher and work there for 4 years and past TSC examination held in 2071 as a secondary level English teacher. After passing TSE examination I was appointed as secondary level teacher in the same school.. I was restricted to access of resources and training Opportunities. People like me belong to new marginalized groups frequently experience overlapping and interrelated systems of discrimination as Crenshaw 1991 argues in her theory of Intersectionality. As a woman from a mixed cast I have to continually negotiate legitimacy and authority as I assumed leadership in a male dominated bureaucratic institution. My leadership password self-navigated molded by residency community path was self-navigated molded by

resilience, community wisdom and an uncompromising dedication to inclusive education rather than being paved with formal mentoring support.

I think both my own experience and the larger institutional and cultural context influenced them in this auto ethnographic narrative. According to Ellis, Adams and Bochner (2011), auto ethnography enables the researchers to examine cultural political and social implications through the prism of personal narratives. This Methodology call decent allows me to recover the narrators that are frequently ignore Improve in this courses on education leadership to recognize the battles and to speak the silences.

Methodology

I have tried to use auto ethnography as a research method. As research a qualitative research technique places the self in a sociocultural context and enables to examine individual experience in light of larger society systems (Ellis, Adams & Bochner, 2011). As it focuses own voices, lived experiences and emotionality, this approach is particularly relevant in feminist research (Jones, Adams, & Ellis, 2016). Using a thematic approach my story draws from my lived experiences over the ten years, critical reflection and memory work. In order to place my experiences within the larger field of women in educational leadership, I also incorporate secondary sources.

Beginning of professional journey

Why I love this profession? I was inspired by my teacher and always dream of being teacher like him. After appearing SLC examination in 2058. Before the result was published I thought of looking for job in schools. I went in two, three schools in my locality but in vain. No one trusted as I had completed my SLC I had no certificate to prove my potentialities. I didn't give up I kept on searching for a job. Finally I was given opportunity to teach in a school as a volunteer. I didn't expect salary from them. I voluntarily worked and after the result was published. I went to India to study. I studied there for two years and after giving final exam I came back to Nepal Waiting for the result. It was 2061, a turning point in my life and beginning of my professional journey. I had completed my +2 from SKD Academy in Lucknow and came back to Nepal. In my locality a new school was opened there was a vacancy announcement and I thought of applying for the post. So I did it accordingly and was selected as Primary teacher. I really enjoyed being with children and teaching them. I gained my experience and learn new ways of teaching them. Deep in my heart I had always dream of being government employee. This keen interest in me kept me striking and I tried to get into government school. I applied thrice in same school but was not selected. Later I realized that ordinary people like me won't be able to get jobs in government school if we don't have any link or political background. By hook or crook I wanted to enter into Government School. Finally I made it through in 2066/10/16. I was appointed as lower secondary PCF teacher. After teaching for 6 years in private school. I started my government school job from 2066. Although the schedule and pedagogical methods of private school were more flexible, they were never firmly rooted in traditional gender stereotypes. I was one of many female instructor who were view through a limited prism as care givers rather than leaders. With the implicit understanding that leadership positions were only for male employees with patriarchal authority we were supposed to be selfless, obedient and caring. The women leaders in institutional and cultural forms this gender.

Expectations were not always clear. For example women are frequently tasked with duties like classroom decoration, student emotional support and parent communication roles cultural ideas of feminist but are not equipped or positioned for leadership post within the institution. Private schools in Nepal frequently function under unofficial hierarchies where patriarchal standards are

still firmly established, restricting women for leadership and career advancement as Bista (2021). I was provided with different coordinator post but was never provided with the responsibility of assistant Head teacher though I performed my task with full dedication and devotion rather than that responsibility was given to principals brother who also worked as a teacher in secondary level. I was assigned to carry out different responsibilities but I was never provided with any official responsibilities. In the beginning I thought it as normal but I later realized that I was being dominated. One of the bitter experience that I would like to state is that working as a government secondary level teachers for more than 10 years I was not provided with any kind of professional development training which remained as hindrance in my promotion to. The condition became more in tolerable when I raised a voice against my principal for not sending me to any kind of training's. Informally the leadership roles were distributed among male educators or those who were his kith and kin. This stage of my career had a significant impact on how I understood the mechanics of institutional power. In settings where opportunity was still determined gender it made me realize that credentials and skill alone were not enough to advance in my professional. My experience is consistent with larger trends in the literature on women in South Asian educational leadership, where women leadership, career paths are carefully but effectively restricted by patriarchal beliefs (Shrestha, 2020; Subedi, 2019)

Methodology

A qualitative research approaches known as auto ethnography blends ethnography and autobiography to examine individual experiences critically in relation to larger Institutional political and social cultural context. Auto ethnography which has its roots in Postmodern and interpreters traditions enables researchers to investigate the ways in Which there lived realities, identities and emotions interact with cultural discourses and Systematic structures (Ellis,Adams & Bochner, 2011). This approach uses story telling as a kind of scholarly research that examines the relationship between the self and society rather than just telling stories for their own sake .

As it emphasizes the resources voice encourages subjectivity and recognize this Emotional and embodiment as legitimate sources of information, auto ethnography is especially important in feminist research (Jones,Adams & Ellis,(2016) Using a thematic approach my story draws the self-reflection of my lived experience in the larger context of women in educational leadership. The various ups and downs that I have overcome throughout my journey from becoming an English teacher to a principal of a government School. Accounts that I present over here will help to scrutinized and reveal recurrent trends, emotional conflicts and turning points in my leadership development.

In order to place my personal story within a larger academic conversation I consult relevant secondary resources in addition to my own experience is such as feminist and educational leadership literature. The complicated and intersecting obstacles that women in Nepali ducational leadership must overcome are made clear by this dual engagement with leave experience and academic theory. This approach enables nuanced and highly contextualized knowledge of how gender, caste ,class and institutional culture influence women's leadership paths in school by fusing personal narrative with academic understanding.

Beginning of my professional journey: Teaching in private school

It was year 2061, after completing my plus to level from India came back to Nepal and joined a private school in Tulsipur. I spend 6 years working as a teacher in a private school which greatly influenced how I perceive institutional culture gender dynamics and professional identity. At first glance the settings seemed more adaptable and lively than in Government schools. Beneath

this flexibility though were ingrained gendered norms and hierarchies that limited the advancement of female educators. In the beginning I was told that I will be provided with the post of accountant but later I was provided as the post of primary teacher. It was the first experience for me being a teacher and beginning of my teaching professional journey. Realise the unwritten rules that government my position as a young woman teacher. It was expected of female educators to exhibit qualities like emotional labor, obedience and nurturing.

Turning point breaking through TSC exam and becoming permanent Secondary level English Teacher

Due to political transition and restructuring of governance TSC examination were not conducted. After a long gap from 2063 finally in 2071 TSC examinations vacancy announcement was done. During this time I was quite busy in taking tuition classes for SLC students and was least concerned about filling the form. I was repeatedly compelled to fill the form by then Education Officer .Unless and until I filled the form he kept on insisting me to fill the form and appear the exam. It was the last day I filled the form as per his wish .Finally examination was held and by gods grace I madeit through written examination .But there was no happiness on my face because I had not prepared well and thought that passing written exam does not guarantee that I would make through interview too. Deep in my heart I had fear of my other competitors. I started inquiring about them and got information that they were teaching Secondary level since long and the perception of other people regarding them was they were intellectual person and there are less chances of my selection. This viewpoints broke me down but there was little rays of hope my English fluency would definitely be my plus point to make it through interview too. Finally a long awaited interview date was declared and went to face interview. Everything went well with very less hope of passing the exam returned back home. Result was published in Gorkhapatra.

During those days we didn't have access to medias or internet .One of my (मीत भाउजू) called me at 11am in the morning congratulated for passing TSC Secondary level English Teacher. I couldn't believe my ears .I repeatedly made her repeat my number for confirmation. I heard of tears following in happiness, on this day I experienced it .Inspite of her confirmation, I wanted to make sure by seeing my symbol number published on newspaper. I asked one of my friends to buy the paper and sent it to me. The next day I received the paper and finally was overwhelmed with joy that I had made it through. It was one of the biggest achievement of my life. From this day I could purely say that I am a government Employee.

Transformational journey from appointment to posting: One side I was very happy for passing TSC examination on the other hand there was fear of being posted to distant place. I was sure to quit if I were posted in distant place I was 7 months pregnant. I didn't dare to go to distant places living family. Many days and night Nightmare kept on torturing me. The Principal of same school where I worked used his power and finally created a vacant post by interchanging some darbandis and I was appointed and posted as Secondary level English teacher in same school .He appeared as God for me during this time. I was really grateful to him for he had done for me. I started trusting him and supporting him in best ways I could. I along with my colleagues took great initiative to use EMI in school. Most of the people in my area had known me and my performance in private sector school. It played vital role to attract students from private school.We succeeded in implementing EMI. Days passed months passed and years passed we performed greatly together. A different reputation we had built in our areas. The flow of students was high. I was assigned with different task without any delay I could perform it in the best way I could. He started calling me dynamic teacher and was awarded with best teacher Award. It was another achievement of my life.

Domination and suppression

Everything was going well. I was happy with my profession .I joined One Year B.Ed and had to do micro teaching practice. I was not given permission in the school and I had to go to another school to do micro teacher. I made sincere request to arrange period in such a way that my teaching practice does not hamper other students class .The rude principal didn't agree to make arrangements as per my requirements I became emotional and heartbroken ,tears flew and couldn't control my emotion .I met my teacher who taught me when I studied in the same school before I joined private school .He made it possible for me .Few days later in the school ,the principal of my school made fun of my tears in the office saying that you cried in front of ABC .Then I spoke against him .It's all because of you if you would have provided me opportunity to conduct micro teaching in school I wouldn't have got insulted there .These words were taken seriously by him .So he started using his power .He assigned me loads of tasks but I completed them without any hurdles .I moved on forgetting the incident thinking there might be some reasons because of which I was not provided with micro teaching class .But next year his sister in law was provided with the opportunity .I realized that to get favorable environment to work either I need to be politically powerful or must be kiths and kins of so called principal. Another bitter experience was training centers kept on sending messages to send for TPD training's but I was never informed and whenever sent to such training. Till today I have been suffering from this pain .My colleagues who were appointed on same date they have completed their TPDs but in my case due to domination I have remained aloof from my professional development .One day training centers staff came to my school to inform about the training and he pinched me saying तपाईंलाई त स्कूल प्यारो छ ,प्र.अ प्यारो छ किन चाइयो ट्रेनिङ ,जति बोलाए पनि आउनुहुन्न। His words hurt me and went to enquire about the training .On hearing this he scolded me like anything in front of others .You don't have trust on me .Why should I do that ? Rather he questioned me if I had filled the form for training .I was not aware about all this things and told him that it was his responsibility to inform his staffs about the training .I was bypassed from the opportunities and all the opportunities were given to his brother who was vice-Principal of the school.Though we were same level teacher. He was appointed as Vice – Principal and was sent to each and every training's. My friends started backbiting saying खुब चुरिफुरी गरि काम गर्छेस काम को मुल्यन्कन हुन्न एहा कसैले तक्मा लाइदिन्न । This words never let me down I kept on telling काम गर फलको आश नगर ।My children loved me it was more than enough for me. There were rapid discussion in education office regarding appointment of Principal in our areas. My principal tried convincing me for not giving my name .He tried his level best to console me but I had made up mind to come out from that school so I gave my name to the team.The burden of expectation : Nearly about 2 years workout finally came into practice in our locality to appoint principals in secondary level School. The so called principal of my school tried his level best to send me to some distance places but as I had got a good reputation in my locality. Political leaders of my locality had already known about my potentialities they supported me in the best way they could. I was appointed as a principal of secondary level school in Tulsipur. It was another milestone achievement for me. Belonging to a Madhesi community born to parents from two different culture. Mother belonging to Chhetri community and father belonging to Yadav community. One our political leader always praised and spoke that he is going to make principal of secondary level School women belonging to different communities one from madhesi community and other from Chaudhary community. He worked accordingly and succeeded in making us Principals. Because of his dedication and devotion we are working in our best way to prove ourselves that we are not less incompetent then the male members. Reaction to my appointment we are not

entirely positive. One of my colleague kept on saying प्र.अ जस्तो जिम्मेवारी पद हाँसेर र छोराछोरी भनेर कहाँ चलाउन सकिन्छ र? This words always reminds me of my responsibilities, dedication and motivate me to do every day better than yesterday. With a dream to shine and to rise I have dedicated myself to bring out the best in my educational and academic journey. In very short period of time I have tried my level best to uplift the quality of my school education. School where I was appointed as a principal had only 250 students after I went there the number of students were doubled. Parents and society members expected changes in the locality in the field of education. Struggle before my presence in school: According to research in leadership roles frequently face higher evaluation requirements and must prove their extraordinary competence in order to be recognized (Poudel & Shrestha). I had to undergo through different struggles. Firstly the principle where I worked t did not provide me the letter of recommendation and secondly the president of school management committee did not allow me to do attendance in the school .Due to the political issues I was not allowed to do attendance, I realized it later .After a long tussle finally dispute was short out and I was given the responsibility. The keen interest to change the Educational system of government school and with a great zeal to do better helped me work out tirelessly. Now getting appreciation from each and every sector adds more energy and enthusiasm within me. Leading government school was not easy job. It has been difficult for women to lead a government school without institutional support. Among the difficulties I encounter where male staff members resistance, community cynicism , leadership development and juggling what and family obligations. I promoted teacher collaboration and used participatory leadership techniques. I found strength in my marginalization experiences and turned them into instruments for environment and empathy (Pant & Rai, 2023)

M.phil. journey in my professional journey a milestone achievement

I never thought that I would do M.phil in my life. I happened to meet one of my friend who persistently supported me to develop in my professional journey. I was the life member of NELTA. I was called in one of the program held in Tulsipur. I shared my views and the domination that I had encountered in my professional journey remaining as a frog of well in a school more than 10 years. As I was kept aloof from the training's that really shaped my professional development. Hearing these our guru offered me to participate in ELTAI conference held in Deharadun .I readily agreed and participated. There I made some of the KU scholars who succeeded in motivating and finally joined KU. This this is journey has really shaped up my professional development journey. I have been recognised as one of the leading women principals in my locality. Opportunity started knocking doors from all sides. I was offered mentorship training, principals training I was started being called a different panel discussions which really helped me to gain popularity in my locality. I would like to remember my professors really inspired me and motivated me in this journey. Their support and dedication has helped me to be a different person in my life. Special thank to one of the beloved professor who has continuously supported me, when I was about to quit this journey. Supporting me continuously and motivated in such a manner to stand again and move on. Your support is incredible. This transformational journey from private school teacher to government school teacher and finally leading as a principal has taught me great lessons. We will definitely be helpful throughout my life.

Intersectionality and identity or two sided sword

I was at the intersection of our overlapping systems of privilege, exclusion and power because of my identification as a woman, someone who was married outside of my ethnic community and

someone who was born into a mix caste household. Bitter experience of being called as a eshini always remains as a nightmare for me. Sometimes I felt invisible not completely welcomed in madhesi community because of my maternal Chhetri ancestors , nor completely accepted in women in kshetriya places because of my madhesi heritage.these infractions became much more complex when I married a Malayali man, full labelled me as culturally different and occasionally even and outside.I frequently experienced minor but stand kinds of explosion in the education system, such as Daud se about my authenticity as a leader social avoidance and its for remarks. These were unpleasant experience and I frequently feel like I had to prove myself all the time in facious where other people were just taken for granted. Gender, caste and ethnicity influenced not only how I for myself in the leadership and teaching field what also how they saw me. This intersectional theory developed by Kimberly Crenshaws in 1989 provides of useful framework for comprehending this intricacy. The concept of intersectionality was how various types of discrimination can coexist and produce distinct marginalisation experiences that are hidden when it considered independently. How about the same intersectionality also turn into a suppressed source of resilience. I was better able to relate and create a bond with kids and educators who felt invisible or unheard due to caste ,language ,gender or socio economic background because of my personal experience of marginalized. I saw the pain behind their quiet and the bravery behind their resistance. Instead of see my identity as a barrier, I started using as a bridge. Rather than following prevailing leadership approaches, I recognised and thrived on my blending .I led with empathy rather than power, I listened instead of giving orders.In many respects, my identity turned into a large blade that could be used as a weapon or as a wound.

Conclusion

More than just a personal story, this auto graphics shops as a mirror reflecting the ongoing struggles and unsung Victories faced by women like myself navigating Nepal challenging educational leadership landscape. It is a story of resiliency in the face of structural neglect, rebellion against patriarchal conventions and rejuvenation via the act of regaining agency and voice. The part to becoming a female principal in a government school was not a straight line, rather it involved able brakes, uncertainty and silent moments of resolve. My experience effects larger structural patterns that many women educators face such as being shut out of professional development opportunities, excluded from leadership pathways and continuously required to the demonstrate their leg legitimacy .Yet I discovered strength in these challenges. I transformed limitations into teachings for improvement and challenges into chances for observation.

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